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ANALYSIS OF INSOLVENCY IN CHEMICAL COMPANIES

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Abstract: This study investigates the financial stability of companies in the chemical industry, focusing primarily on the Indonesian and Indian stock exchanges. Given the industry's critical role in the global economy, the research analyzes key factors contributing to insolvency risk in chemical companies, examines the impact of operational inefficiencies, and assesses the influence of regulatory and market factors on financial stability. Utilizing quantitative methods for bankruptcy prediction, such as the Altman Z-score and Springate S-Score, the study evaluates the financial data of several companies across different countries. The findings underscore the importance of liquidity management, operational efficiency, and proactive regulatory compliance in mitigating insolvency risks.

Key words: insolvency, bankruptcy, chemical companies, Altman Z-score, Springate S-Score, liability, assets, supply chain disruptions, working capital, EBIT.

INTRODUCTION

Assessing the financial stability of companies is crucial, as most businesses experience periods of distress that can lead to insolvency. The chemical industry plays a pivotal role in the global economy, supplying essential materials to sectors such as pharmaceuticals, agriculture, and manufacturing. According to the American Chemistry Council (ACC), the economy depends on chemistry at four levels: the direct production of chemicals; industries that use chemicals to manufacture raw materials or intermediate inputs; consumer goods industries that either purchase chemicals directly or use chemically processed components; and wholesale, retail, and service sectors reliant on chemically derived products [1].

Despite its critical role, the chemical industry faces significant financial risks due to volatile raw material prices, stringent regulations, intense competition, and other global challenges. The insolvency of chemical companies can trigger widespread consequences, including job losses, supply chain disruptions, and economic instability. Understanding the factors leading to insolvency is essential for stakeholders to develop effective risk mitigation strategies.

This research aims to identify key financial indicators signaling insolvency risk in chemical companies, analyze the impact of operational inefficiencies on financial health, and assess the influence of regulatory and market factors on the financial stability of these firms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The chemical sector is generally prosperous. However, as mentioned, some companies face financial difficulties. When a company becomes insolvent, several models can be used to predict bankruptcy.

One of the key indicators of insolvency is leverage ratios (or solvency ratios). As noted in the *Guide to the Business of Chemistry* by the ACC (2023), leverage ratios assess a company's debt levels relative to other financial metrics. A common example is the debt-to-equity ratio, which compares total debt to shareholders' equity.

Another widely used insolvency evaluation method is the Altman Z-Score Model. This model helps predict the probability of financial distress within a two-year period. Initially, an internal credit scoring system was developed to assess external bonds and evaluate the likelihood of default. The Z-Score model was later validated on steel companies, demonstrating 85–90% accuracy. The study concluded that while the model is accurate, simple, and accessible, it is not flawless due to Type II Errors (Altman, 2006) [2]. Over time, the formula has been expanded through various studies, making it applicable across multiple industries, including manufacturing, services, retail, technology, utilities, healthcare, and both public and non-public sectors. According to the model:

- $Z > 2.90$ is categorized as a safe or healthy zone.
- $Z < 1.13$ is considered a high-risk bankruptcy zone.
- Companies falling between these values are in the gray zone, indicating financial uncertainty.

Another bankruptcy prediction model is the Springate Analysis Model (S-Score), developed in 1978 by Gordon L.V. Springate. It was designed as an extension of the Altman model (A. Anwar & R. R. Utami, 2022) [3]. Springate's research involved 40 companies and demonstrated an impressive 92.5% accuracy in predicting financial distress.

Recent research by Ratnasari, I., Nugraha, N., & Sutardiyanta, I. (2024) highlighted the significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the global economy, particularly in Indonesia. The pharmaceutical industry, for example, experienced a decline in demand for non-COVID-related products. Lockdowns in China and India disrupted the supply chain, affecting over 90% of the raw materials used in Indonesia's pharmaceutical sector. Additionally, the number of chronic disease patients visiting hospitals dropped significantly, and dentist services were temporarily halted, leading to slower growth for certain pharmaceutical products [4]. Similarly, global recessions have severely impacted chemical companies, pushing many toward insolvency.

Several researchers have applied different bankruptcy prediction models to assess financial risks, particularly for chemical companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange. Likewise, Indian analysts Othman, M. S., Nagina, R., and Saini, A. applied the Altman Z-Score methodology to 40 firms. Their findings revealed that:

- 30 companies fell within the Healthy Zone,
- 7 companies were in the Gray Zone, and
- 4 companies were classified in the Bankruptcy Zone [5].

This classification system provides investors and stakeholders with valuable insights into financial distress and associated risks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted using quantitative research methods, including analysis, synthesis, data collection, and comparison. Data was gathered from financial reports, income statements, cash flow statements, and balance sheets of chemical companies in different countries. The research paper and collected data represent the insolvency rate of these firms, assessed using the Altman Z-score, Springate S-score, and other bankruptcy prediction models.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Priyanto P. (2022) [6] analyzed the financial position of PT XYZ, Indonesia's largest and most comprehensive fertilizer company, between 2016-2020. According to the Altman Z-score model, the company experienced financial distress during the given period.

The Z-score formula is as follows:

$$Z = 1.2 \times (WC/TA) + 1.4 \times (RE/TA) + 3.3 \times (EBIT/TA) + 0.6 \times (MVE/TL) + 1.0 \times (S/TA)$$

Where:

- **WC/TA** – Working Capital / Total Assets
- **RE/TA** – Retained Earnings / Total Assets
- **EBIT/TA** – Earnings Before Interest and Taxes / Total Assets
- **MVE/TL** – Market Value of Equity / Total Liabilities
- **S/TA** – Sales / Total Assets

Table 1. Results of the Fifth Z Score of PT XYZ from 2016–2020.

Year	WC/TA	RE/TA	EBIT/TA	MVE/TL	S/TA
2016	0.0303	0.3707	0.0816	0.9128	0,6436
2017	0.0329	0.3567	0.0600	0.9513	0,5759
2018	0.2431	0.0570	0.0798	0.8710	0,5954
2019	-0.1854	0.0746	0.0807	0.8438	0,6368
2020	-0.0872	0.0987	0.0759	1.0719	0,6419

Table 2. PT XYZ category Z-score.

Year	Value Z Score	Category Z Score
2016	1,6150	Grey zone

2017	1,4862	Grey zone
2018	1,4306	Grey zone
2019	1,1711	Grey zone
2020	1,3478	Grey zone

Findings from PT XYZ's Financial Data (Table 1):

Working Capital to Total Assets (WC/TA): From 2016 to 2018, the company's working capital relative to total assets was positive. However, in 2019 and 2020, it turned negative. This indicates that in the last two years, the company's short-term debts exceeded its short-term assets, signaling financial difficulties.

Retained Earnings to Total Assets (RE/TA): The company's retained earnings remained positive over the five-year period, demonstrating reliance on internal profits rather than external debt for financing.

Earnings Before Interest and Taxes to Total Assets (EBIT/TA): A positive EBIT/TA ratio indicates that the company effectively utilized its assets to generate sufficient revenue to cover operating costs.

Market Value of Equity to Total Liabilities (MVE/TL): This ratio remained positive over the five-year period, suggesting that the company did not face severe solvency issues. However, if the average value was close to zero, it implies that the company was at risk of solvency problems, as its assets were barely sufficient to cover its liabilities.

Sales to Total Assets (S/TA): The company's sales-to-total-assets ratio remained positive on average over the five-year period, reflecting efficient asset utilization for revenue generation.

Based on the Altman Z-score results (Table 2) [7], PT XYZ was categorized within the grey zone, meaning it was neither fully solvent nor in severe financial distress. The company's Z-score ranged between 1.17 and 2.90 over the years. Notably, in 2019, the Z-score fell to 1.17, indicating that the company was on the verge of entering the distress and bankruptcy zone. However, proper regulatory measures and strategic policies helped the company recover from this situation.

Table 3. Calculation of Bankruptcy analysis with Altman Z-score.

Issuer Code	Year	Z-Score	Prediction	Reality	Conclusion
DVLA	2018	4.3370	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2019	4.3376	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2020	2.8103	Grey Area	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2021	3.0723	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2022	3.2830	Non Distress	Distress	Wrong Prediction
KAEF	2018	1.8311	Grey Area	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2019	1.2010	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
	2020	0.7110	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
	2021	0.7657	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
	2022	0.7710	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
KLBF	2018	6.6237	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2019	6.0659	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2020	4.5637	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2021	4.5068	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2022	4.6694	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction

MERK	2018	1.7818	Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2019	3.8571	Non Distress	Distress	Wrong Prediction
	2020	2.8713	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
	2021	3.9538	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2022	2.8326	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
PYFA	2018	3.0278	Non Distress	Distress	Wrong Prediction
	2019	3.1077	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2020	2.7755	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
	2021	1.6650	Distress	Non Distress	Wrong Prediction
	2022	6.4282	Distress	Distress	Correct Prediction
SIDO	2018	6.5670	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2019	4.3816	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2020	2.7450	Non Distress	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2021	2.7137	Grey Area	Non Distress	Correct Prediction
	2022	4.2143	Grey Area	Non Distress	Correct Prediction

The data presented in Table 3 shows the results of the bankruptcy analysis conducted on pharmaceutical companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2018 to 2022 using the Altman Z-score model by Ratnasari, I., Nugraha, N., and Sutardiyanta, I. [4]. Based on this analysis, across 6 companies over 5 years, with a total sample size of 45, it was predicted that 20 firms were at risk of bankruptcy, 4 were in the grey area, and 21 were in a healthy state. The predictions had an accuracy rate of 86.67% (39/45 correct) when compared to actual conditions.

Othman, M. S., Nagina, R., and Saini, A. [5] analyzed the position of the Indian pharmaceutical industry, considering a broader sample size that included companies across large, medium, and small market capitalizations. The study examined 40 firms.

Figure 1. Average Altman Z-score Analysis of 10 selected large cap.

Figure 2. Average Altman Z-score Analysis of 10 selected mid cap.

Figure 3. Average Altman Z-score Analysis of 10 selected small cap.

The research conducted on large-cap pharmaceutical companies illustrates a positive financial outlook (Figure 1). The Z-score of each company Sun Pharmaceutical Industries, Dr. Reddy's Laboratories, Lupin Limited, Divis Laboratories Limited, Zydus Lifesciences, Alkem Laboratories Limited, and others was high enough to place them in the healthy zone, with a minimum score of 3.69.

Figure 2 represents Indian pharmaceutical companies in the mid-cap segment, showing almost similar results. All 10 companies maintained a solid financial position during 2016–2023. However, one company, Wockhardt Ltd., experienced continuous financial distress starting in 2017. The average Z-score for this firm was 1.55.

For small-cap companies, the situation was significantly different, as depicted in Figure 3. Only two firms Alpa Laboratories and Albert David Limited remained in a healthy state, with scores above 3.70. In contrast, Lyka Labs and Wanbury had scores of 0.62 and 0.12, respectively, indicating insolvency. The other six companies were in the grey zone, neither fully healthy nor bankrupt.

The findings of this study indicate that market size plays a crucial role in the solvency of companies. Analyzing PT XYZ's financial situation, it was observed that its WC/TA ratio was initially positive but turned negative in 2019 and 2020. Most financial metrics reflected positive numbers, leading researchers to conclude that while the company was not in immediate distress, some strategic changes were necessary. Given that PT XYZ was close to bankruptcy in 2019, Priyanto (2022) and other researchers recommended the following actions:

Increase total sales by fully utilizing the new plant's capacity while being cautious and selective with investments to reduce liabilities.

Address working capital issues by improving business operations, selling unnecessary fixed assets, or negotiating with the government for outstanding payments related to fulfilling government fertilizer allocations.

Consider loan funding for future development projects.

For pharmaceutical companies in Indonesia, the analysis indicates that firms with the issuer code KAEF experienced financial distress for four consecutive years (2019–2022). Similarly, MERK (3 years), PYFA (2 years), and SIDO (2 years) were also in distress or within the grey zone. Notably, the WC/TA ratio for KAEF was significantly low, even turning negative at -0.26% in 2019 and -3.95% in 2020. A low WC/TA ratio signals poor liquidity, whereas strong companies require high liquidity to sustain operational working capital and drive profits through increased sales.

On the Indian stock exchange, most chemical companies found in the grey and distressed areas were medium- and small-cap firms. To mitigate potential risks for companies in the grey zone such as Venus Remedies Ltd., Bafna Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Take Solutions Ltd., Brooks Laboratories, and others risk management strategies and proactive financial planning are critical measures (Jiayuan et al., 2018) [8]. The number of insolvent firms in the chemical sector remains very low, not only within this study but also across the country. As observed in the mentioned figures, large-cap companies generally maintain a high Z-score, mid-cap firms exhibit similar financial health, whereas small- and micro-cap companies face significant financial challenges.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The chemical industry faces financial challenges, particularly for companies with smaller capacities. In recent years, insolvency issues were primarily driven by the impact of COVID-19. However, according to Alex Tullo, the global chemical industry has recovered from the pandemic and is now benefiting from higher prices [9].

The use of models to assess insolvency is crucial for identifying potential financial risks in advance. Various models employ different formulas tailored to specific industries and sectors. In this research, the Altman Z-Score model proved to be the most accurate in predicting the bankruptcy of chemical companies. It correctly identified financial distress in 39 out of 45 tested companies in Indonesia, achieving an accuracy rate of 86.67%. In some cases, this figure exceeds 90%.

Other models, such as Springate (S-score) and Zmijewski (X-score), can also be utilized, as they demonstrate efficiency and accuracy in financial distress prediction. The research findings provide valuable insights for further development and can assist investors in making informed investment decisions. Additionally, this study offers a practical approach to assessing financial distress, applicable to both manufacturing and non-manufacturing organizations.

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